

First Graduate Representation in the Academic Council, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, National University of Jujuy (Argentina, 1990)

(ENGLISH TRANSLATION)

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences

National University of Jujuy (Argentina)

This document certifies that Verónica Pereyra Carrillo was officially appointed as a Graduate Council Member of the Academic Council of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, National University of Jujuy, for the 1990 academic period.

This appointment recognizes her formal participation within the institutional collegiate governance structure of the Faculty.

Issued by the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, National University of Jujuy.

(End of document – signatures follow)